

FATTY ACID-BASED DIISOCYANATE SYNTHESIS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF GREEN POLYURETHANES

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Abstract – Aiming to the development of new synthetic routes for polyurethanes (PU) from raw materials exclusively from renewable sources, a 'green' synthesis of 1,8-diisocyanatooctane (DIO) was carried out from fatty acid derivatives by a method without the use of phosgene. The three-step synthetic route started from dimethyl sebacate, with the preparation of decanedihydrazide and decanedioyl diazide as intermediates, under nitrogen atmosphere. FTIR and ¹H NMR analyses confirmed the structure of the diisocyanate, which is a promising 'green' alternative to be used in the production of more sustainable polyurethanes by reaction with suitable polyols from biomass.

Keywords: Isocyanate, fatty acids, renewable sources, green synthesis.

Introduction

Polyurethanes (PU) are the result of the reaction between polyols and di- or polyisocyanates. Due to its chemical versatility, it is possible to adapt to many structures, by selecting the most suitable polyol or isocyanate for the desired purpose. Sometimes, its synthesis is carried out through chemical routes that do not consider its adverse consequences, using raw materials derived from fossil products and substances harmful to health, for example [1]. However, the search for potential raw materials from renewable sources that resemble or exceed the efficiency of these materials, mainly from the oil industry, has gained great prominence in the scientific community [2]. In the literature, there are numerous attempts to replace materials from the petrochemical industry or create new materials from renewable sources [3-4].

The preparation of isocyanates to produce PU can occur in numerous ways, although the most used method on an industrial scale involves the reaction between gaseous phosgene (COCl₂) with amines or their corresponding salts [5]. The high toxicity, combined with the growing environmental appeal, has led to the development of new routes for the preparation of isocyanates without the use of phosgene. Lossen, Curtius and Hoffmann rearrangements, and the use of phosgene equivalents such as di and triphosgene, for example, are some of the alternative methods employed for its replacement. In this perspective, there are fatty acids, such as sebacic acid, which is a naturally occurring dicarboxylic acid, which is still little explored for obtaining isocyanates [6]. Studies have shown that isocyanates from fatty acids, when reacted with a suitable polyol, can improve the thermal properties of PU [3,7].

Therefore, in this work we propose the synthesis and characterization of an isocyanate from a renewable source from sebacic acid derivatives, for the production of 1,8-diisocyanatooctane (DIO).

Experimental

Dimethyl sebacate synthesis

Dimethyl sebacate was produced according to the procedure described by Kunkuma et al. [8]. In a 200 mL kitassato, 15 g (74 mmol) of sebacic acid 99% (Sigma Aldrich), 2 mL of sulfuric acid 95 – 97% (Biotec) and 100 mL of methyl alcohol 99,8% (Honeywell) were added at 65 °C for 5 hours. At the end of the reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, being extracted with ethyl acetate 99,5% (Reatec) (200 mL). The organic phase was successively washed with water (4 times of 50 ml) until neutral pH. Anhydrous sodium sulfate 99% (Dinâmica) was used for drying the organic phase. With the rotary evaporator, the solvent was removed. Purification was carried out on a silica gel column, using a mixture of hexane and ethyl acetate 99,5% (Reatec) (v/v, 95:5) as eluent, resulting in the end dimethyl sebacate in liquid form. Final mass obtained: 16.8 g. Yield: 99%.

Fatty acid based isocyanate synthesis

The isocyanate synthesis route was based on the produced reported by More et al. [3], involving three steps to obtain 1,8-diisocyanatooctane (DIO) (Figure 1).

Step 1: Synthesis of decanedihydrazide (DDH)

In a round bottom flask were added dimethyl sebacate (32 g, 138.94 mmol), hydrazine hydrate 99% (Sigma Aldrich) (34.77 g, 694.74 mmol) and ethanol 96% (Honeywell) (150 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred at 35°C for 48 hours under a nitrogen atmosphere. At the end, the rotary evaporator was used to evaporate the excess of solvent, obtaining a white powdery solid.

Step 2: Synthesis of decanedioyl diazide (DDD)

In step 2, dihydrazinedecane (4 g, 17.39 mmol) was reacted in a beaker kept cooling at 0 °C with a solution of concentrated hydrochloric acid 37% (Reotec) (6.34 g, 173.91 mmol) and acetic acid 98% (Cinética) (10 mL). Soon after 30 mL of dichloromethane 99,9% (Scharlau) were added. Then, under vigorous stirring, an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite 97% (Dinâmica) (6.48 g, 93.91 mmol + 15 mL of water) was slowly dropped onto the reaction mixture. After the completion of the addition, the reaction mixture was kept under stirring for 30 minutes at 0 °C. In the next step, the organic phase was separated and washed with a 0.1 mol·L⁻¹ aqueous solution of sodium hydrogencarbonate 99,7% (Dinâmica) (twice), followed by a 0.1 mol·L⁻¹ solution of sodium chloride. Finally, drying was performed with anhydrous sodium sulfate. The solvent was evaporated with the rotary evaporator at room temperature.

Step 3: Synthesis of 1,8-Diisocyanatooctane (DIO)

In the third and last step, the previously prepared DDD (3 g, 11.60 mmol) was mixed in a round bottom flask with tetrahydrofuran 99% (Dinâmica) (40 mL) under a nitrogen atmosphere for 6 hours. After completion of the reaction, the solvent was removed using a rotary evaporator. Then, 10 mL of petroleum ether was added to the compound and passed through a silica gel column to purify the substance. Finally, the compound was rotary evaporated to evaporate the solvent.

Characterization

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) has been performed in a Bruker INVENIO-S equipment. The samples were measured in transmission mode at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution, from 450 to 4,000 cm⁻¹.

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) was measured in a Bruker AVANCE III HD 400MHz spectrometer, using deuterated chloroform (CDCl₃) as a solvent.

Figure 1 – Synthesis route for DIO production.

Results and Discussion

Initially, the characterization of the synthesized dimethyl sebacate was carried out, a necessary reagent for the synthesis of diisocyanate. FTIR and ^1H NMR spectra were performed and compared with a commercially available dimethyl sebacate standard (Sigma Aldrich). The main absorption bands related to the main functional groups present in the structure of the molecule were observed, such as -C=O and -C-O- ester bonds. The ^1H NMR spectra also allowed the identification of the hydrogens present in the dimethyl sebacate structure. Kunkuma et al. (2013) in their studies for the synthesis of dimethyl sebacate, reported the same trends observed in the FTIR and ^1H NMR spectra for both the synthesized and the commercially available molecule, indicating success in the synthesis.

The FTIR spectra (Figure 2) show the absorption bands of the synthesized diisocyanate. In the initial stage of DDH formation, two absorption bands with moderate intensity are observed at 3310 and 3291 cm^{-1} related to the presence of the -NH_2 and -NH functional groups, while at 1629 cm^{-1} there is a strong absorption typical of amide carbonyl. For the DDD formation stage, at 2135 cm^{-1} the appearance of a strong band can be observed, which can be attributed to the presence of azide (N_3) in the molecule. At 1706 cm^{-1} a band of strong intensity is due to the presence of the carboxyl that directly performs a chemical bond with the azide (-CON_3). Finally, for the spectrum of obtaining octane 1,8-diisocyanate (DIO) at 2256 cm^{-1} , a strong absorption relative to the formation of the isocyanate bond (NCO) in the molecule is observed. More et al. [3] describe similar results for the synthesis of DIO regarding the formation of absorption bands, corroborating the spectral profiles obtained.

Figure 2 – FTIR spectrum for the synthesized isocyanate: 1,8-diisocyanatoctane (blue), decanediol diazide (red) and dihydrazinedecane (black).

Figure 3 shows the ^1H NMR spectrum for the synthesis of DIO performed in DMSO-d_6 . For the stage of obtaining the DDH, the chemical shift relative to hydrogen ($-\text{NH}-$) of the amide bond is observed at 8.92 ppm (s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CONHNH}_2$). At 4.15 ppm (s, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CONHNH}_2$) shifts of the primary hydrogens ($-\text{NH}_2$ -) of the amide are formed. The chemical shift of 1.98 ppm (t, $J = 7.75$ Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CO}$) is attributed to the neighboring hydrogens of the carboxyl present in the DDH structure. It is also observed the formation of a peak between 1.35 – 1.55 ppm (m, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{CO}$) attributed to the chemical displacement of the distant hydrogens in two chemical bonds of the amide carboxyl. Finally, at 1.10 – 1.25 ppm (m, CH_2) the formation of a peak is seen relative to the hydrogens internal to the chain, which consequently are further away from the $-\text{C}=\text{O}-$ bonds of the amide, suffering less influence in their chemical shift values.

Also in Figure 3, the ^1H NMR spectrum for DDD, which was carried out in CDCl_3 , can be seen. This shows at 2.26 ppm (t, $J = 7.13$ Hz, CH_2CO) a chemical shift attributed to the neighboring hydrogens of the azide carboxyl. The region around 1.40 – 1.60 ppm (m, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{CO}$) refers to hydrogens separated by two carboxyl bonds. Peaks at 1.10 – 1.30 ppm (m, CH_2) are attributed to the main chain methylenes, which suffer less influence from the carbonyl in their chemical shifts.

Finally, for the DIO spectrum (Figure 3), which was performed in CDCl_3 . It is observed at 3.23 ppm (t, $J = 6.83$ Hz, CH_2NCO), the appearance of a small peak related to the chemical shift attributed to the neighboring hydrogens to carboxyl. At 1.40 – 1.60 ppm (m, $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{CO}$) we have the chemical shift relative to the distant hydrogens in two carboxyl chemical bonds. In the region of 1.10 – 1.30 ppm (m, CH_2), we observe the formation of peaks related to the $-\text{CH}_2-$ bonds internal to the chain, which suffer less influence from the carboxyl in their chemical shifts.

The patterns of ^1H NMR chemical shifts are similar to those obtained in the work developed by More et al. (2013) for the synthesis of new isocyanates based on fatty acids, where the authors synthesized DIO following a synthetic route similar to that described here.

For the three stages of synthesis to obtain DIO, it was observed that the generated spectra presented coherent and characteristic chemical shifts for each of the synthesized compounds, which were very similar to the studied literature. Based on this, it is possible to state that the isocyanate of interest for this work was successfully synthesized.

Figure 3 – ^1H NMR spectra for the synthesized isocyanate: DDH (blue), DDD (red) and DIO (green).

Conclusions

The synthesis of octane 1,8-diisocyanate was successfully performed from renewable raw material, without the use of phosgene, by a 'green' synthesis using fatty acid via diacyl hydrazine intermediate. The presence of the main functional groups in the diisocyanate structure can be observed through FTIR spectroscopy. ^1H NMR spectra confirmed that DIO had formed. The synthesized diisocyanate presents itself as a promising 'green' alternative to be used in the synthesis of polyurethanes.

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